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ANALYSIS OF AIDA MODEL WITH VIEWER'S CHOICE OF SELECTED TV PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

Today, television is playing a pivotal role in the socialization of people. It has become a major source for entertainment and to provide knowledge. The programs and shows broadcasted on television influence people in undesirable ways. People tends to spend a lot of time watching television irrespective of any age groups. The study was conducted to know the choice of viewers with respect to television channels and programs people tends to watch more in tier-2 city. The study was conducted among the people of Davangere city to identify the reasons, preference and frequency of time spent in watching the selected programs and shows. A sample of 200 respondents were taken for the analysis. Chi-square test, Garret Ranking and Frequency Analysis were used to know the choice of viewers. The study also highlighted the parameters the viewers choose for watch the particular shows and programs by using the AIDA model.

KEYWORDS: Viewer's choice, Program preference, Time spent, Online Platform, AIDA model, Tier-2 cities.

INTRODUCTION

The Indian television industry is a booming sector for the economy and has seen tremendous growth over the years. The industry has been largely driven by increasing digitalization and higher internet usage over the last decade. With the growing effect of streaming sites and online television like Voot, Hotstar, Amazon Prime etc. there is an upward trend towards Over-the-Top (OTT) platforms. As of 2012, the country has a collection of free and subscription services over a variety of distribution media, through which there are over 823 channels of which 184 are pay channels. Total television viewership of 415 million is amongst the world's highest with nearly 15-16 Television companies beaming programmers to India. India ranked at 15th in the world in music industry, with the buoyant performance of the industry and is expected to enter into the top 10 music markets by 2022.

According to the studies conducted by the researchers, people watch television most often and spend about 3-5 hours daily. With the growing number of availability of new channels, the choices of viewers have been scattered among many shows and programs broadcasted in various channels. Over the past few decade television has made a permanent place in the homes of India. Accessibility to television and OTT platforms is increasing day by day and has been accepted by the society. varieties of programs like news, serials, reality shows, documentary shows, sports etc. are available at any time.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Devadas M B and Dr. B K Ravi (2013) did an empirical study on the urban youth of Bangalore city regarding the cultural impact of television. The researcher has found that the television has an impact on culture norms of the youth.

Dr. Artta Bandhu Jena (2014) did an empirical study on the television watching habits of 15 to 25-year age viewers. The researcher has found that the mentioned age group prefers to watch Tv programs more rather than playing games or reading books. The respondents like to watch Tv for more than 3 hours per day.

Dr. K Aparna (2015) did a study on television viewers of rural and urban areas of Nizamabad district. The researcher has found that both rural and urban viewer's preference for watching television are quite similar irrespective of any gender, occupation, age.

V. Vijay Kumar and S Arulchelvan (2015) did a descriptive research on reality shows and their impact on the viewers. The researchers found that the reality shoes have a definite impact on viewers in terms of emotional affiliation.

R Pugalendhi (2015) did a study on Chennai urban women regarding popularity of television programs. The researcher has found that both homemakers and working women have similar trend in their viewing habits. According to the study television plays major role in the lives of the Chennai urban women's.

S Hemanthkumar and Mohit Kallur (2016) did a study considering the impact on personality of an individuals because of television viewing habit. The researcher has found that the genre that impacts on personality and television viewing has a significant difference with each other except music genre.

Arti Bhatt and Dr. Govind Singh (2017) did a study on rural women of Tehri Garhwal district about the television watching habits. The researcher has found that television has become a major source of entertainment for the rural women irrespective of any age, educated or uneducated, working or domestic women.

Md. Morshedul Islam (2018) identified the viewing pattern and program choice among rural and urban people in Bangladesh. The researcher has observed that rural viewers prefer to watch programs in Bengali Language whereas urban respondents like to watch programs in Hindi and English.

C Karthila, P Vijayalakshmi and Maya L Pai (2018) did a study on viewing pattern and habits of people in Kerala. The researcher has found that Tv viewing and programs preference are affected by demographic factors.

Vishal Kohli and Rajendra K Jain (2019) did a study on perception of viewers. The researcher has found that each viewers have different perception and different behaviour.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study has been conducted to identify the viewer's choice with respect to selected television programs in Davangere city. The specific objectives of the study are as follow:

1. To identify the frequency and time spent on watching Tv.
2. To identify the reasons behind the viewing the selected Tv program.
3. To identify the Tv channels viewed by the people in Davangere.
4. To identify most preferred Tv programs by people in Davangere.
5. To analyse AIDA model with respect to the viewer's choice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study has been conducted in Davangere city, Karnataka. The survey was carried out on 200 respondents. the data was collected personally in the months of January 2020 and February 2020. For the purpose of research convenience simple random sampling technique was used.

The questionnaire comprised of a rank question, close-ended questions, a 5 point likert scale questions. The data which was collected through questionnaires was coded and tabulated keeping in context with the objective of the study. It was further suitably analyzed by calculating percentages by using frequency analysis, Garret Ranking technique and Chi-square test. The data was analyzed using IBM SPSS v22 throughout the study.

DATA ANALYSIS

Socio personal profile of the respondents: N=200

CHARACTERSTICS	NO. OF RESPONDNETS	PERCENTAGE
GENDER		
Female	162	81%
Male	38	19%
AGE		
18-22	54	27%
23-27	45	22.5%
28-32	26	13%
33 and above	75	37%
OCCUPATION		
Homemakers	68	34%
Student	77	38.5%
Employee	50	25%
Government Employee	5	2.5%
FAMILY TYPE		
Joint Family	55	27.5%
Nuclear Family	145	72.5%

Table No: 1 Demographic Data

As mentioned in Table No 1 Out of 200 respondents, 81% respondents were female and 19% were male. 27% viewers belong to the age group that lies around 18-22. 22.5% viewers belong

to the age group that lies around 23-27. 13% viewers belong to the age group that lies around 28-32. 37% viewers are from age 33 and above. Among them 34% respondents are Homemakers. 38.5% are the college students. 25% respondents were private and self-employees and 2.5% respondents were government employees. 27.5% viewers belong to joint family and 72.5% viewers belong to nuclear family. Here in this survey family played a major role for knowing the reasons and purpose of watching television programs and shows.

SITUATION FOR WATCHING

SITUATION	NO. OF RESPONDNETS	PERCENTAGE
Travelling	9	4.5%
On Holidays	85	42.5%
During Work or study Break	28	14%
During Eating	78	39%
Total	200	100%

Table No: 2

According to the survey 42.5% of viewers i.e. 85 respondents like to watch programs and shows during their holidays. 39% of respondents i.e. 78 viewers like to watch the telecasted shows during eating. 14% of viewers i.e. 28 respondents like to watch the shows during their study break of work break. The remaining 4.5% of respondents i.e. 9 viewers like to watch the programs during travelling.

OTT PLATFORM PREFERED BY THE RESPONDNETS

PLATFORM	NO. OF RESPONDNETS	PERCENTAGE
Hotstar	12	6%
Voot	40	20%
Amazon Prime	16	8%
Jio TV	44	22%
Others	88	44%
Total	200	100%

Table No: 3

OTT platforms the respondents like to use to watch the shows other than television. Among them 6% of respondents i.e. 12 viewers like to watch through Hotstar. 20% respondents i.e. 40 viewers like to watch through Voot application. 8% respondents i.e. 16 viewers like to watch through Amazon Prime. 22% respondents i.e. 44 viewers like to watch through Jio Tv. The remaining 44% respondents i.e. 88 viewers choose others. (Refer Table No: 3)

PURPOSE OF WATCHING

PURPOSE	NO. OF RESPONDNETS	PERCENTAGE
Reduce Stress	96	48%
Gain Knowledge	34	17%
Bonding with Family	52	26%
Opportunity to Travel	8	4%
Logical & Analytical Reasoning	8	4%
Total	200	100%

Table No: 4

In the table it shows that 48% viewers i.e. 96 people watch television because it reduces stress. 17% viewers i.e.34 respondents watch television to gain knowledge. 26% viewers i.e. 52 respondents watch television because it helps them in bonding with family. The remaining 8% viewer's watch television because it gives them the opportunity to travel and helps them in Logical and analytical reasoning.

FREQUENCY AND TIME SPENT ON WATCHING TELEVISION

TIMINGS	NO. OF RESPONDNETS	PERCENTAGE
6AM-9AM	13	6.5%
12PM-4PM	1	0.5%
4PM-7PM	24	12%
7PM-12AM	85	42.5%
As Per Convenience	77	38.5%
Total	200	100%

Table No: 5

According to the figure, 13 viewers i.e.6.5% likes to watch television around 6am-9am whereasonly0.5% of viewers like to watch television during 12pm-4pm. Another 24 viewers i.e. 12% like to watch television late afternoon which is around 4pm-7pm. 85 viewers i.e.42.5% likes to watch around 7pm-12am. The remaining 77 viewers i.e.38.5% of people like to watch television as per their convenient timing.

REASON BEHIND WATCHING THE SELECTED TV PROGRAMS

REASONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Content/Story	80	40%
Anchor/ Actor & Actress	46	23%
Curiosity Creation	24	12%
Script/Narration	23	11.5%
Emotional Attachment	27	13.5%
Total	200	100%

Interpretation:

Most of the viewers watch the shows and programs due to the content or story of the program. Among 200 respondents 80 viewers gave the reason saying they watch the particular shows or programs because they like the content or story of the program. 46 viewers prefer to watch their favourite shows because of the anchor/ actor & actress. 24 viewers watch the programs because of the curiosity creation by the program. 23 viewers watch the shows because of the narration of the story. And remaining 27 viewers watch the shows because they have emotional attachment towards the program.

KANNADA TV CHANNELS VIEWED BY PEOPLE IN DAVANGERE CITY**MOVIE CHANNELS**

MOVIE CHANNELS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Colors Kannada Cinemas	88	44%
Udaya Movies	73	36.5%
Star Suverna	21	10.5%
Public Movies	9	4.5%
Amoga Movies	9	4.5%
TOTAL	200	100%

Table No: 6

Among the movie channels in Kannada, respondents prefer to watch more Colors Kannada Cinemas. Among 200 responses 44% respondents prefer to watch Colors Kannada Cinemas. 36% respondents prefer to watch Udaya Movies. 10% respondents prefer to watch Star

Suvena. 5% respondents prefer to watch Public Movies and remaining 5% respondents prefer to watch Amoga Movies.

Garret Ranking:

According to Henry Garret Ranking method, the responses given by the viewers are calculated based on the formulas:

1. For Counting the ranks given by respondents we use the formula:

$$= \text{countif}(\text{range}, \text{criteria})$$

2. To calculate percent position, the formula used is:

$$= 200(R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$$

Where, R_{ij} = ranks i.e. 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10

N_j = Total ranks given by the respondents i.e. 10.

NEWS CHANNELS

NEWS CHANNELS	RANKS
TV9	1
BTV	2
Suvena News	3
Public Tv	4
Janashree News	5
News18 Kannada	6
Samaya	7
Raj News	8
Kasturi News	9
DD Chandana	10

Table No: 7

The above table shows the ranking given to the news channels as per the preference of respondents by using Henry Garret Ranking method. As per the response the highest priority i.e 1st rank is given to “TV9 news” channel. The moderate priority is given to “Janashree News”. Whereas least priority i.e.10th rank is given to “DD Chandana”.

CHANNELS

CHANNELS	RANKS
Zee Kannada	1
Colors Kannada	2
Colors Super	3
Kasturi Tv	4
Udaya Tv	5
Udaya Comedy	6
Suverna Plus	7
Shankara Tv	8
Star Sports Kannada	9
DD Chandana	10

Table No: 8

The above table shows the ranks given to different Kannada channels as per the priority given by the respondents by using Henry Garret ranking method. As per the figures the highest priority is given to “Zee Kannada channel” whereas Moderate priority is given to “Udaya Tv” channel and least priority is given to “DD Chandana”.

MOST PREFERRED TV PROGRAMS BY PEOPLE IN DAVANGERE.**PREFERENCE**

CRITERIA	RANKS
News	1
Movies	2
Tv Serials	3
Reality Shows	4
Music	5
Sports	6
Documentary Shows	7
Horoscope & Devotional	8
Comedy	9
For Shopping	10

Table No: 9

As shown in the table, garret ranking is given to criteria which the viewers prefer for watching in Kannada channels. As per the tables shown above the highest preference i.e. 1st rank is given to “News” then comes “Movies” i.e. 2nd rank then following “Tv serials” which is given 3rd rank. The least preference i.e. 10th rank is given for the “Shopping”.

SERIALS PREFERED

SERIALS	RANKS
Agni Sakshi	1
Magalu Janaki	2
Jothe Jotheyali	3
Gattimela	6
Mangala Gowri Madhuve	5
Lakshmi Barama	8
Subalakshmi Samsara	7
Mithuna Rashi	9
Seetha Valabha	10
Kamali	4

Table No:10

The above table shows Garret ranking given for the serials as per the preference of the viewers. As we can see the highest preference i.e. 1st rank is given to the serial “Agni Sakshi” following “Magalu Janaki” which is givrn 2nd rank. The 3rd rank is given to the serial “Jothe Jotheyali”. The least preference i.e. 10th rank is given to serial “Seetha Valabha”

REALITY SHOWS PREFERED

REALITY SHOWS	RANKS
Big Boss	1
Weekend with Ramesh	2
Sa Re Ga Ma Pa	3
Drama Juniors	4
Dance Karnataka	6
Comedy Kiladigalu	5
Kannadada Kotyadipathi	7
Kannada Kogilay	9
Shantham Papam	8
Super Minute	10

Table No: 11

The above table shows the Garret Ranking given to the Reality Shows as per the viewer's response. The highest preference i.e. 1st rank is given to reality show "Big Boss" then comes "Weekend with Ramesh" i.e. given 2nd rank then following "Sa Re Ga Ma Pa" which is given 3rd rank. the lowest preference i.e. 10th rank is given to reality show "Super Minute".

AIDA MODEL WITH RESPECT TO VIEWER'S CHOICE

SD- Strongly Disagree

A- Agreed

DA- Disagree

SA- Strongly Agreed

ND- Neither Agree nor Disagree

PARAMETERS	SD	DA	ND	A	SA
The characters in the show have held my attention.	12	8	16	120	44
The content / story of the program has held my attention.	5	9	25	95	66
The narration of the story has held my interest.	8	9	58	74	51
The flow of emotions of each character has made me emotionally attached with the program	16	26	29	102	27
By watching shows & serials, it helped me in updating myself to current trends.	15	26	57	70	32

I share the information about the Tv programs with my friends and family regularly.	20	23	28	86	43
I always advice my friends and others to watch the programs I like most	18	29	29	66	58

Table No: 12

As shown in table, when it comes to the Attention variable in AIDA model, most of the respondents agreed that the character and the content/ story of program or shows have held their attention. When it comes to Interest variable in AIDA model, most of the respondents agreed that narration of story as well as the flow of emotions have created more interest in them towards the programs or shows. When it comes to Desire variable in AIDA model, most of the respondents agreed that by watching shows and programs it helped them in updating to current trends of society whereas 57 respondents neither agree nor disagree because they might have felt the trends shown in programs are not appropriate to them or might have disliked them. When it comes to Action variable in AIDA model, the respondents agree that they share the information about the Tv programs and suggest them to watch the particular programs telecasted.

DISCUSSION

According to the research, approximately 43% of viewers prefer to watch TV shows and programs during Holidays following 39% of viewers prefer to watch Tv during consumption of their food. It is found that 48% of viewer's watch Television to reduce stress where as 26% of viewer's watch Tv to bound with their family. When it comes to watching schedule, approximately 43% of viewer's watch TV during 7pm-12am whereas approximately 39% of people watch television as per there convince.

40% of viewers watch the selected Tv programs because of the story or content of it. Whereas 23% of viewers watch the selected Tv program because of the Anchor or Actor and Actress. Another ~13% of viewers watch because they are emotionally attached with the shows and programs. 44% of viewer's watch "Colors Kannada Cinemas" when it comes to watching a movie in the channel whereas approximately 37% of viewers like to watch movie in "Udaya Movies channel".

When it comes to watching News channel, as obtained from Garret Ranking, most of the viewer's prefer to watch News from "TV9" following "BTV" then from "Suverna News". The least preferred channel for watching news is "DD Chandana". As obtained from Garret

Ranking, most of the viewers prefer to watch shows from “Zee Kannada” then following “Colors Kannada”. The least preference is given to “DD Chandana”.

When it comes to watching the shows from the channel, as obtained from Garret Ranking, most of the viewers prefer to watch News then following Movies then comes the Tv Serials. The least preference is given to Shopping from the Tv Platform. When it comes to serials preferred by the viewers, as obtained from Garret Ranking, the first preference is given to the serial “Agni Sakshi”. The second preference is given to “Magalu Janaki”, following “Jotha Jotheyali”. The last preference is given to the serial “Seetha Valabha”. As obtained from Garret Ranking, the first preference is given to Reality show “Big Boss”. The second preference is given to “Weekend with Ramesh”, following “Sa Re Ga Ma Pa”. The least preference is given to “Super Minute” Reality Show.

CONCLUSION

Davangere city consist of the viewers of Kannada programs which is a local language and people get connected with the stories of the serial and shows. Most of the serials and shows get clicked by the senior citizens and homemakers. Most of the viewers get connected with the family oriented stories and are inspired by them.

When a study is conducted on people of Davangere city, regarding the choice of viewers towards selected Kannada Tv Programs, it has come to light that people like to watch the particular serials or shows because it helps them in coping up with their stress and also helps them to have bonding with their family.

As per the responses given from the viewers, major respondents prefer to watch news. when it comes to reality shows “Big Boss” has made its top 1 position in the minds of viewers. Even though the serial “Agni Sakshi” has made its end the viewers gave major priority to it. The viewers gave the reason for watching the selected shows and programs because of the content /story of the program has held their attention along with the programs characters i.e. the actor or actress.

The shows and programs telecasted are playing major role in the life of viewers by making them emotionally attached to it. Trough watching the programs the viewers are updating to the latest trends as well as gaining knowledge through them. The viewers are sharing the information about the programs and shows which are being telecasted with their family and friend and becoming a topic for discussion. These shows and programs are keeping people of Davangere city most entertained and are making them get connected with the virtual characters of the show by inspiring and motivating them.

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